

Conceptual Background

Promoting Coastal Resilience through Participation and Living Labs within the mareXtreme mission

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1 Introduction

Coastal regions are increasingly exposed to extreme marine events and natural hazards such as geo- and biological hazards, floods, storm surges, droughts, terrestrial and marine heatwaves. Climate change is expected to intensify both the frequency and severity of these events, amplifying risks for coastal ecosystems and the communities that depend on them. Their impacts typically unfold at local and regional scales, often triggering cascading and cumulative effects, and nonlinear processes, i.e., earthquakes and subsequent tsunamis in the Mediterranean, or marine heatwaves, algal blooms, and resulting hypoxia in the Baltic Sea and other marine basins. Addressing these dynamics requires comprehensive observation systems, improved hazard modelling across scales, and robust early warning systems, combined with close engagement and empowerment of responsible and affected actors. Strengthening coastal resilience ultimately depends on a deep understanding of system behaviour, potential tipping points, and collaborative approaches that integrate scientific, governmental, industrial, and community perspectives.

Against this backdrop, the German Marine Research Alliance (DAM) mission *mareXtreme* – Pathways to Improved Risk Management of Marine Extreme Events and Natural Hazards brings together around 150 researchers from 29 partner institutions to advance the scientific and societal capacities needed to manage such risks. Through its four interconnected projects - ElbeXtreme, METAscales, MULTI-MAREX, and PrimePrevention - the mission investigates how short-term, multiple, and compound extreme events interact with long-term changes in marine ecosystems and coastal societies. *mareXtreme* aims to significantly enhance the predictability of marine extreme events, support sustainable coastal development, and strengthen the resilience of both ecosystems and communities. Central to this mission is a transdisciplinary, participatory research approach that establishes Living Labs as collaborative spaces where scientists, local actors, and community multipliers jointly develop solutions tailored to specific regional risks and needs. This approach ensures that real-world, cross-sectoral knowledge informs effective risk management under changing climate conditions.

In light of these challenges and the mission's ambition to advance both scientific and societal capacities for dealing with marine extreme events, the objective of this conceptual background paper is to establish a shared understanding of the basic principles that guide transdisciplinary research within *mareXtreme*. Coming from four different project contexts, backgrounds and objectives we identify differences and similarities in order to work for synergies and common concepts for participation and Living Labs in coastal hazardous situations. In *mareXtreme* it includes bringing together predominantly sustainability-oriented community development with technically oriented innovation initiatives, e.g., early warning systems, nature-based solutions, etc., to enhance coastal resilience. We jointly reflect on the framework conditions and requirements for participation and problem-focussed, solution-oriented research, and to examine the concept of Living Labs in the context of the mission's work. What does participatory Living Lab work provide to the core goals of the *mareXtreme* mission, to the way research is conducted, and its potentials for dealing with hazards in coastal systems? Do we need a new, independent concept of real-world participation to continue pursuing our mission's goals?

To this end, the paper i) clarifies key terms and concepts related to participation and Living Labs to foster a shared understanding across projects and disciplines; ii) synthesizes insights into the application of participatory methods by identifying differences and commonalities across the four *mareXtreme* projects; iii) examines the scales and levels at which these projects engage with the Living Lab approach; and iv) critically discusses opportunities and challenges that arise when applying this research framework in the context of marine extremes and coastal resilience. Our common goal in *mareXtreme* is to work towards a blueprint for coastal Living Labs as research infrastructure to help address, manage and cope with marine hazards.

2 Concepts, historical roots and key terms related to participation and Living Labs

In this first section, we introduce participation as a foundational element of the transdisciplinary research conducted within *mareXtreme* to be societally relevant (see Fig. 1). We then trace the historical roots and evolution of Living Labs as a methodological approach for participation in research projects. In doing so, we refer to Living Labs as a research infrastructure, depending on the context, to illustrate its versatile interpretation and application across different periods and settings. We then clarify terms related to the variety of ‘co-processes’, which we understand as distinct forms of participation within the Living Lab approach. Finally, we provide a short synthesis of working definitions for *mareXtreme*, including a glossary of key terminology.

Figure 1: Conceptual framework of participation, Living Labs, and ‘co-processes’ as the organisational structure for this paper.

2.1 Participation

What is participation and why is it relevant?

Participation in transdisciplinary research can be understood as the collaborative act that integrates diverse knowledge systems by engaging communities, policymakers, lay-people, and scientists in a co-creative research process (Reed et al., 2008). Such participatory approaches are more than information provision or consultation. They often take the form of workshops, group discussions or other interactive formats that capture public attitudes, perceptions, beliefs, and knowledge, which are factors that affect the success of management plans. Indeed, evidence shows that management plans may fail when users and interest groups are insufficiently involved in planning and decision-making (Sowman & Sunde, 2018; MacAskill, 2019). Therefore, participatory approaches are essential to better understand the management of complex and dynamic social-ecological systems and to foster wide-ranging engagement in required transformation processes, such as in the context of *mareXtreme*.

Conceptualizations of participation in research processes have evolved since the 1960s. One of the initial frameworks is Arnstein's (1969) "ladder of citizen participation," which visualizes participation as a series of steps representing different degrees of involvement by non-academic actors. Building on this, Krütli et al. (2010) categorize public participation into four groups — information, consultation, collaboration, and empowerment — ranging from one-way information flows to relevant interest groups to higher levels of involvement where knowledge is exchanged and decision-making power is transferred to non-academic actors. More recently, Parsons et al. (2025) have proposed a new typology in the context of climate mitigation, adaptation and resilience research. Their framework responds to ongoing debates about participation, arguing that existing models insufficiently address power dynamics. While concerns about power imbalances and exclusion of minority groups were already raised in the 1960s (Arnstein, 1969), progress in addressing these issues has been limited (William, 2004). Drawing on a systematic literature review, Parsons' et al. (2025) new typology aims to challenge structural inequalities in an emancipatory participation process along a continuum (rather than within discrete categories, see Figure 2 below) to emphasize the interconnectedness of participation, including domination, exclusion, negotiation, and transformation (see Fig. 2).

Despite differences in conceptualization, these frameworks share a common recognition that participation is not a singular act but a dynamic process involving varying degrees of engagement and influence towards collective action. In *mareXtreme*, we therefore understand participation as a foundational element of actor- and user-centred problem-solving and solution-orientation within Living Labs. We draw on these typologies to guide responsible and inclusive engagement with non-academic actors throughout our research processes.

This diagram illustrates the four main stages of participation, emphasizing the complexity of participation as a continuum, which is nonetheless non-linear, with multiple feedbacks (both positive and negative) that can advance or impede participatory processes contributing to transformative changes. Positive pathways are depicted by the forward arrows, and negative pathways are depicted by the backward-facing arrows).

Figure 2: Diagram of Continuum of Participation (Parsons et al. 2025).

2.2 Living Labs

What is the history of the ‘Living Lab’ concept and how did it get disseminated in Europe and Germany?

The Living Lab concept has emerged through a diverse historical trajectory that links technological experimentation, participatory practices and socio-spatial inquiries. Good ideas usually have many parents, and it is not easy to forensically reconstruct where exactly the roots of this research method lie. In this chapter, we trace the beginnings of Living Labs, a concept that builds on a tradition of user-centred participatory research, but has gained momentum and new directions with the emergence of computer technologies and the sustainability discourse. It extends earlier approaches that emphasized the active involvement of users in innovation processes. In the literature, two dominant roots of today’s Living Lab methodology can be identified: A Scandinavian-European tradition and a US-American one. The US-American strand, particularly coined through the work of William J. Mitchell at the Massachusetts Institute of Technology (MIT) in the early 2000s with early home-based and technology-driven Living Laboratories, played a decisive role in shaping the contemporary concept and the subsequent institutionalization. Mitchell and his team are also widely (and inaccurately as we will illustrate below) credited with being the first to use the term ‘Living Lab’ in the sense discussed here (EnoLL, 2025; Hossain et al., 2019; Rujsink & Smith, 2016; Garcia Robles et al., 2015; Ballon & Schuurmann, 2015). The chronology is best understood by first tracing the foundational roots, which have in common that they did not yet use the term Living Lab, and then subsequently examine the development of the concept as a research method in more detail.

Scandinavian roots

In the Scandinavian strand, one example is the *Scandinavian Cooperative and Participatory Design Movement* in the 1960s and 1970s when designers began to rethink how work could be carried out with people rather than for them. Instead of treating users as distant sources of requirements, these early initiatives explored more collaborative and dialogical ways for designers and non-designers to work together (Göransdotter, 2022). This movement contributed principles of co-creation, real-life contexts, participation and social innovation resulting in a user-centred design-approach (UCD). Later on, European social experiments with information technology emerged as another predecessor of the Living Lab methodological approach: originating from psychology, social experiments were conducted outside of laboratory settings (Cook & Shadish, 1994). Supported by European Commission programs, such as FAST (Forecasting and Assessment in Science and Technology), these IT experiments aimed to explore how Information and Communications Technology (ICT) could reshape organizations and society (Qvortrup, 1987). They found practical application in field-trials with Interactive Videotex, broadband cable networks, computer conferencing systems and rural telecentres. The experiments applied a reciprocal learning process between users and technology providers, in which technologies evolved in response to user experiences and users' adaptation to new possibilities (Ancelin, 1987; Hartley, 1987). Another early European Living Lab approach is the 1990s '*digital city*' concept. Digital cities, such as Amsterdam and Helsinki, focused on cooperation between various actor collaborations for network infrastructures and platforms to provide citizens with more information, which gave the concept a distinctly technology-oriented character (Ballon & Schuurmann, 2015). In this context, the private sector became increasingly important as it participated in testing and involving technology users into its product development through the use of Living Labs.

US-American contexts

US-American roots of Living Lab implementations under this label can be traced back to the two schools of the Georgia Institute of Technology (GIT) and the Massachusetts Institute of Technology's (MIT) Media Lab in the 1990s. Accordingly, the work of Bajgier and colleagues (1991) at Pennsylvania's Drexel University is often overlooked. But they already used the term 'Living Laboratory' in a paper about how students applied methods within communities, engaging local residents and interdisciplinary problem-solving in-situ rather than in traditional classroom or laboratory settings (Bajgier et al., 1991; Nesti, 2018; Radulescu et al., 2022). So, clearly this early articulation co-exists in literature prior to MIT's prominence.

The main lead can be recognized in human-computer-interaction (HCI), where the Living Lab concept was used to investigate the contextual requirements for designing and evaluating people's interactions with technologies (Alavi et al., 2019). Notable projects such as GIT's *Aware Home* (Kidd et al., 1999) and *Classroom 2000* (Abowd et al., 2000) as well as MIT's *PlaceLab* (Intille et al., 2006, 2005) pioneered the creation of instrumented living environments equipped with sensors to investigate ICT and context-aware services.

The *Aware Home Research Initiative*, a project constructing a 3-story 470 m² facility aiming to explore how computing technologies in residential environments could support everyday living, was initialized in 1998 and began its operational phase in May 2000 (Abowd, 2002). The *Aware Home* can be recognized as the first residential laboratory and a significant precursor of modern Living Labs. The MIT *PlaceLab*, opened in 2004, was designed as a fully equipped 93 m² residential environment in which voluntary participants temporarily lived for days or weeks while their activities, routines and

interactions with home-based technologies were continuously recorded by an extensive sensor and data collection infrastructure (Intille et al., 2006, 2010). According to Intille et al. (2010), unlike other Living Lab environments, *PlaceLab* features a building-wide and synchronized sensor infrastructure that collects data not just in isolated test areas. This unique data environment enables researchers to study everyday activities holistically over a longer period of time and distinguishes *PlaceLabs* from other Living Labs with more fragmented data collection.

Conceptually, William J. Mitchell and colleagues at MIT Media Lab are the most influential and ground-breaking in terms of the specific design of Living Labs as they formalized the idea into a research methodology for technology innovation. Within constructed and specially configured laboratories they conducted systematic recording, prototype development and refinement of technologies in smart/future artificial homes, while hidden participant observation took place (Eriksson et al., 2006). Methodologically, this setup extends conventional usability testing by enabling long-term observation of everyday practices. Consequently, they generated more realistic user data and captured implicit knowledge in situ, but the participants were primarily seen as passive subjects, whose interactions with technology were tracked for later analysis (Ballon & Schuurman, 2015; Pierson & Lievens, 2005).

Transition to European environments

In the early 2000s, Mitchell's participation in the Expert Advisory Group of the *IntelCities* project, an EU-funded initiative focused on urban digital innovation, facilitated the transition from US-Living Lab ideas into the European context. Nevertheless, the 'new' concept, also drawing on the above-mentioned earlier experiences with participatory design, social experiments and digital cities from the 1960s to 1990s in Scandinavia, represented a fundamental reinterpretation of the US-originated labs based on home-like setups. A key distinction evolved with the focus on studying users within their everyday environments, rather than recreating everyday contexts in a laboratory setting (Niitamo et al., 2006). Therefore, methodological-wise, testing environments were from now on brought to the users, rather than requiring users to come to the lab (Ballon & Schuurmann, 2015).

At this point, it becomes clear that the two historical roots of modern Living Labs differ in the way that early US Living Labs were primarily academically driven and typically situated in small-scale laboratories or artificially constructed homes. Their focus was on controlled experimentation. In contrast, the European strand of Living Labs is extended to neighbourhood and regional scales, embedding experimentation within public spaces and institutional settings to address broader societal challenges and enhance policy relevance (Eriksson et al., 2006; Schuurman & Leminen, 2021).

At the *IntelCities* project's conclusion, participating municipalities agreed in 2006 to establish a European network for exchanging knowledge on Living Labs, the *European Network of Living Labs* (ENoLL), under the Finnish EU Presidency. *ENoLL* institutionalized, formalized and expanded the Living Lab concept into a multinational, methodologically more coherent movement. It initially encompassed 19 Living Labs in 15 EU member states (Radulescu et al., 2022) and since its implementation *ENoLL* certified almost 500 Living Labs worldwide, coherent with growing academic interest indicated by a gradual increase of publications referencing the method (ENoLL, 2025; ENoLL, 2022). Through *ENoLL*'s establishment, the historical linkage to experimenting with ICT diversified into

various thematic foci such as health & wellbeing, mobility, energy or social innovation (Schuurman & Leminen, 2021; Tötzer et al., 2020; ENoLL 2025).

The key elements of a Living Lab, as identified by the *European Network of Living Labs* (ENoLL), include:

- 1) **active user involvement:** engaging users as co-creators rather than passive subjects in the innovation process,
- 2) **real-life setting:** conducting research and testing in natural, everyday environments rather than artificial laboratory setups,
- 3) **multi-stakeholder participation:** collaboration among diverse stakeholders, including users, companies, public organizations, and researchers,
- 4) **multi-method approach:** utilizing a variety of research methods to gather qualitative and quantitative data,
- 5) **co-creation:** encouraging joint development of solutions through active collaboration between users and developers.

These elements ensure that Living Labs foster user-centric innovation and bridge the gap between research and practical applications (Ruijsink & Smith, 2016).

From user observation to collaboration - and beyond

As shown above, the history of the Living Lab concept ranges from technologically controlled smart-home laboratories in the US to more participatory, real-life-embedded, collaborative innovation platforms in Europe. Over time, this evolution included a broader shift from pure human-behaviour-observation out of business interests into strategically empowering human agency by detaching laboratories from their traditional understanding and 'bringing them to life' (Tötzer et al., 2020). Living Labs in their modern understanding and their historical roots have in common that they can be understood as research infrastructures that bring together co-design and co-production practices, active user involvement, real-life contexts, multi-actor collaboration, and diverse experimental testing-methods. While on the one hand, the technologically centred testbed MIT-approach and live testing of new technologies continues to be important (see section on *Reallabor-Gesetz* below), the socially embedded, citizen-driven innovation systems, which are addressing societal challenges and transforming communities gained momentum. Rather than recreating realistic contexts within a constructed laboratory, contemporary Living Labs are embedded in actual everyday environments, such as homes, neighbourhoods, public spaces or work environments with a conceptual shift from user observation to active co-design, co-creation and co-production (ENoLL, 2025; Stuckrath et al., 2025; García Robles et al., 2015).

Following the initial conceptualization of Living Labs as primarily technology-focused research environments in the late 1990s and early 2000s, the European Commission has focused on strengthening European competitiveness and actively promoted Living Labs as strategic instruments. The EU approach extends the conventional notion of an innovation-driven model and understands Living Labs as a strategic instrument to foster multi-actor partnerships, with a particular emphasis on placing citizens at the heart of co-creation and collaborative processes (Nesti, 2016). By its explicit inclusion of non-academic knowledge holders from the onset in the research process, Living Labs thus go beyond classical case study research approaches.

In 2019, the European Commission started *Horizon 2020*, a program for research and innovation. Since then, Living Labs have also grown into instruments of research and

innovation infrastructures for tackling societal and environmental challenges (ENoLL 2025). Accordingly, a combination of scholars and practitioners working on urban sustainability transformations as well as researchers in sustainability science explicitly connected Living Labs to sustainability transformations and socio-technical change (Radulescu et al., 2022; Bouwma et al., 2022; von Wirth et al., 2018). In Sweden, for example, Living Lab initiatives such as the *Botildenborg Social Innovation Living Lab* in Malmö bring together universities, municipal authorities, regional actors and civil society to co-create socially and ecologically resilient solutions that span food systems, social integration, and community wellbeing (SLU, 2024). Another example is the Government of Canada's 10-year program '*Agricultural Climate Solutions – Living Labs*', which supports a nationwide network of Living Labs where climate-friendly farming methods are developed and tested directly on agricultural land. These initiatives, which span several provinces including Manitoba, Prince Edward Island, Quebec and Ontario, bring together farmers, researchers, indigenous communities and other partners to jointly explore, refine and share sustainable solutions (Bancerz, 2021). This expansion of the historical ICT focus demonstrates the capacity of modern Living Lab methodology to integrate sustainability into practice and learning processes.

Conceptual Ambiguity and Methodological Challenges of Living Lab Research

Based on the increasing differentiation, proliferation and observed popularity of Living Lab concepts and methods, it is not surprising that the term has become a buzzword in the meantime. The term is mushrooming. 'Living Labs' appear in many contexts and the term is used loosely across diverse settings and with many meanings, not always in the sense in which they originated. Radulescu et al. (2022) argues that the diverse implementations cannot only be seen as versatility alone but also as a conceptual drawback and a lack of consistency: Living Labs transformed into a term with multiple interpretations and various definitions across different domains and activities across the globe. Consequently, several researchers in the meantime are missing a conceptual and methodological specification and a clear distinction between technology-based innovation testing in Living Labs and a deeper understanding or reflection of social practices as well as guided societal transformation processes (Franz, 2015; Leendertse et al. 2016). Nonetheless, Living Labs evolved into a widely recognized method that generates a broad range of benefits for knowledge-production as well as knowledge-transfer and facilitates transdisciplinary development through user-involvement on local scales (Bouwma et al. 2022).

Living Labs in Germany

The establishment of Living Labs in Germany was mainly driven by sustainability-oriented research and science policy debates. It is not so deeply rooted in ICT-driven approaches like the above-mentioned origins and it has been initialized rather late in international comparison. A key driver was the realization that conventional disciplinary research formats were insufficient to address the upcoming social-ecological challenges such as climate change, energy transition and urban transformation (Liedtke et al, 2012; MWK, 2013; Schneidewind & Scheck, 2013; Geibler et al., 2013; Beecroft & Parodi, 2016; Jahn & Keil, 2016; Kern & Haupt, 2021). Moreover, the debate has intensified with the 'experimental turn' in sustainability science since the early 2000s, which increasingly focused on intervention, testing solutions to sustainability challenges and transdisciplinary knowledge production (Schäpke et al., 2017; Parodi & Seebacher, 2024).

The decisive institutional breakthrough for Living Labs (translated into German: *Reallabore*) in Germany started with a proposal by Uwe Schneidewind, at that time Scientific Director of the Wuppertal Institute for Climate, Environment and Energy, who suggested promoting *Reallabore* as a tool for transformation research to the German Parliament's Committee on Education, Research and Technology Assessment in 2012 (Schneidewind, 2012; Wagner, 2017). Subsequently, the state of Baden-Württemberg established an expert group on 'Science for Sustainability'. Based on its findings, the state government pioneered in framing the *Reallabor* as a key instrument for promoting a transdisciplinary, sustainability-oriented research approach with a leading role for Germany as a whole (MWK, 2013) and further implemented them in the sustainability strategy of 2014 (Ministry for the Environment, Climate and Energy Baden-Württemberg, 2014; Bauer, 2018; Kern & Haupt, 2021). This culminated in 2015 in the introduction of the *BaWü-Labs* funding lines, which formally embedded *Reallabore* in regional research funding structures and enabled long-term, transdisciplinary experiments in urban and regional contexts (Kern & Haupt, 2021). The conceptual work of the Wuppertal Institute for Climate, Environment and Energy made a decisive contribution to transforming earlier ideas of real-world experiments (e.g., Gross et al., 2005) into a research format geared towards transformation (Jahn & Keil, 2016; Wanner et al., 2018) and their methodology is closely linked to policy-oriented, applied and sustainable transformation research. Another key actor was the Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (KIT), who developed a theory-driven and conceptually explicit approach based on the *District Future – Urban Lab* launched in 2011 and the *Reallabor131: KITfindetStadt* starting in 2015 on Karlsruhe's Oststadt district. These projects emphasize Living Labs as long-term research infrastructures for sustainable development, embedded in urban contexts, while hosting multiple experiments and based on integrative sustainability concepts (Parodi et al., 2016a; Parodi et al., 2016b, Parodi & Seebacher, 2024).

Accordingly, Baden-Württemberg served as an early incubator, but since the mid-2010s Living Labs spread at the federal level through funding programs such as the BMBF's *Future City Initiative*, launched in 2015 as part of the framework program "Research for Sustainable Development" (FONA³), and other federal funding infrastructures (Wanner et al., 2018; Kern & Haupt, 2021; Federal Ministry of Education and Research, 2015). They promoted activities in other research institutes and universities. Living Labs expanded nationwide, especially through large-scale idea-competitions since 2019, as a method for various topics, including urban sustainability, mobility, energy systems and digitalization. As a result, their relevance in Germany is gradually growing in political and scientific debates as an increasingly standardized research infrastructure within German sustainability research, even though conceptual clarity and methodological coherence continue to pose challenges.

Living Lab / Reallabor – Roots and Institutionalization of Living Labs

Figure 3: Roots and institutionalisation process of Living Labs

Gefördert durch:

Living Lab or Real-world Laboratory?

In Germany, 'Living Lab' got translated into 'Reallabore' and in the process of working it got translated back into rather clumsy *Denglish* as 'real-world laboratories' (Wiefek et al. 2024). Parodi and Seebacher (2024) stated that in Germany, a specific form of transdisciplinary experimental lab was developed during the course of European developments in the early 2000s. Under the term *Real-world Labs* (RwL, in German: Reallabor) they consider Living Labs as "places and incubators to develop and research sustainability solutions, or, in a nutshell, to experiment and examine desirable societal futures with scientific means" (p. 421). As "institutions of change", Parodi and Seebacher (2024) declare the intention of this kind of research work "[...] to support, research and accelerate the "Great Transformation" of settlements in particular (WBGU, 2016)" (p. 421).

A RwL refers to a transdisciplinary (TD) research facility designed to conduct experiments in a spatially defined societal context (Parodi et al. 2016). RwLs comprise aspects of lab design, real-world or transformative experiments, and interventions (Kampfmann et al. 2023). RwLs aim to initiate transformation processes and to sustain corresponding scientific as well as societal learning processes (Parodi et al. 2016). Reflection on the assumed impact pathways is pivotal for the consolidation and transferability of the results gained in RwLs (Schneidewind and Rehm 2019). For Wiefek et al. (2024) discussion around concepts, approaches, criteria, and methods is particularly important in order to avoid confusion and ambiguities and with a shared understanding to ensure successful implementation.

For our context in *mareXtreme*, it will be important to find common ground based on the origins of Living Labs work and to identify the distinctiveness and singularity of coastal Living Labs in dealing with extreme events. This also includes bringing together predominantly sustainability-oriented community development with technologically oriented innovation initiatives and merging it towards coastal Living Lab approaches.

What contributes to and how does it deviate from the German 'Reallabore-Gesetz'?

The German 'Reallabore-Gesetz' (short: ReallaboreG) refers to a draft legislation introduced by the current German federal government to the national parliament on 19 June 2025 (print 21/517) for the "improvement of framework conditions for trial of innovation in Living Labs and for promoting regulatory learning". The text of this draft legislation is identical to an initial proposal that the national parliament deliberated at a first reading at the end of May 2025 (print 21/218). The *ReallaboreG* shall strengthen Living Labs as an important instrument for promoting innovation - with a strong emphasis on technical innovations. Even though the draft explicitly aims to include social innovations, the applied concept of Living Labs focuses on serving as a facilitator for testing groundbreaking new climate and environmentally friendly technologies and concepts, and they offer the opportunity to gain insights into the impacts, opportunities, and risks of these innovations through such testing (see Reallabore-Gesetz, 2025). The draft legislation shall help overcome obstacles of legal regulation that often make innovations inconsistent with existing law. The new law will define terms and establish requirements for a unified and innovation-friendly approval regime. As a supporting tool, the federal government will set up a Living Lab innovation portal that facilitates the implementation of Living Labs in the German context with appropriate actions. This link to innovation policy and law is the main feature that distinguishes a Living Lab from a *Reallabor* (German context). While the German Reallabore-Gesetz may broaden and streamline the regulatory space for testing technological and administrative innovations, its implications for participation,

co-creation, and social innovation remain limited. Yet these dimensions are central to strengthening societal resilience to coastal extreme events in *mareXtreme*, where shared agency, and community-embedded preparedness processes are indispensable. In this regard, the law supports experimentation, but it does not address the deeper social and societal dynamics and processes that Living Labs rely on to enable effective responses.

How are Living Labs defined in other coastal and marine contexts in Germany?

Living labs are no new phenomena in coastal realms. As being participatory and experimental, their potentials “...facilitating and guiding successful knowledge exchange at the interface of science and society” and they contribute as an operational framework “...when having to deal with multiple, overlapping challenges in the context of ocean governance” (Franke et al., 2022). Franke et al. (2022) perceive Living Labs as “...still under-explored but are a tangible way for addressing the societal challenges of working towards sustainability transformations over the coming UN Ocean Decade and beyond (Franke et al. 2022).

In Germany, there are several examples with diverse understandings of what the Living Lab approach is about and how Living Labs should be performed. The pilot study ‘Eckernförder Bucht 2030’ had the aim to establish a Living Lab and contribute to the protection of biodiversity, the improvement of water quality and thus to the achievement of the EU MSFD objectives and the HELCOM Baltic Sea Action Plan ([‘Eckernförde Bay 2030’](#), Germany). In the project ‘Gute Küste Niedersachsen’ ([‘Good Coast Lower Saxony’](#), Germany, 2020-2025) the focus was on investigating and promoting ecosystem strengthening coastal protection in the Lower Saxony North Sea coast by i) collaborating with responsible authorities on reliable planning and approval (Kempa et al., 2023) and ii) establishing a scientific infrastructure at Spiekeroog coastal observatory for monitoring the land-sea transition zone (Zilienski et al., 2022). In Sankt Peter Ording, North Sea, a transdisciplinary research initiative on coastal protection and nature conservation is undertaken in the research project [“Sandküste St. Peter-Ording”](#) with the objective to enhance the ecological quality of the coastline, provide protection against storm surges, and adapt to climate change by strengthening natural processes. The project did not begin as a Living Lab endeavour, but over the course of the project it developed the typical characteristics of transdisciplinary collaboration, featuring collaboratively developed technical solutions and testing them in real-world settings. Even though it did not start with the Living Lab label, this technical, solution-oriented approach, involving the relevant coastal protection and nature protection authorities, NGOs and the municipality, the project can be considered as constituting a Living Lab approach (Winter et al., 2025). (For further international examples, see Franke et al., 2022).

In the DAM (Deutsche Allianz Meeresforschung) living Labs are understood as real-world experimental spaces where researchers and societal actors work together to address complex, context-specific problems. They highlight the role of experiments within the approach, which relates strongly to the literature on technological innovation. However, they also highlight opportunities for transformation, which can be understood as social innovations. The *SpaCeParti* project in the DAM mission *sustainMare* has adopted the Living Lab concept and established two maritime Living Labs in their project work: One on a coastal education trail and another one educating sea rangers (see website: <https://www.spaceparti.de/en/living-lab/>).

The following core characteristics they set for their maritime Living Lab:

- has a thematic containment
- has a geographical prescription
- has real-world problems as a starting point
- is an experimental space in which ideas for solutions to real-world problems are conceived, tested and evaluated
- is therefore a space in which
 - learning processes take place through reflection and variation of solution approaches
 - knowledge transfer between stakeholders and science takes place in this way
 - transdisciplinary work is carried out
- is designed for the long term in order to build trust and to be able to initiate and accompany structural and social change
- makes a contribution to sustainable development in the frame of reference sea-land/society-nature.

Section summary

In summary the Living Lab approach represents a significant shift in research methodologies, emphasizing user involvement and real-world experimentation and testing to foster innovation as well as to steer necessary social and political transformation processes. As the concept continues to evolve, it holds the potential to address multifarious societal challenges through collaborative and user-centred design processes and solution-oriented strategies. Ongoing research and practice in Living Labs will be crucial for not only developing technologies that are innovative, but also to foster socially relevant processes that are applicable, beneficial, and sustainable. However, despite the successes of Living Labs, challenges remain, including the need for effective and lasting collaboration among diverse actors, decision-makers and lay-people, in addressing systemic innovation aspects. Depending on the focus and objective direction of a Living Lab, there is a need to highlight the importance of public-private partnerships, the role of lay-people, and the role of municipal governments in driving innovation and sustainability transformations. In Living Lab initiatives, it remains crucial to prioritise enhanced user participation and the addressing of broader societal issues, ensuring that processes of societal transformation and technology development align with user needs and community values. This guarantees vital, serious and fair participation on an equal footing for all actors involved and affected communities.

2.3 Participatory approaches in Living Labs through 'co'-processes

What is co-creation, co-design, co-development, co-evaluation and co-production?

Building on the central role of participation in Living Labs, the following descriptions of 'co'-processes illustrate how participatory engagement is operationalised and referred to across disciplines and sectors. These approaches represent distinct but complementary ways of structuring collaboration between academic and non-academic actors.

Co-creation is often regarded as the overarching approach (Vargas et al., 2022; Nyguen et al., 2024). In the Living Lab context, transdisciplinary research can be understood as a co-creation process that integrates co-design, co-production, and co-evaluation (Franke et al., 2022). It brings together scientists, practitioners, organizations, and citizens to generate knowledge, develop solutions, and ensure that outcomes are practice-oriented and responsive to real-world needs. It is frequently defined as the joint creation of value, highlighting multiple experiences and the active participation of end-users such as practitioners and citizens, and is considered essential to social innovation (Voorberg et al., 2014). While co-creation is seen as an ideal type of transdisciplinary research, attention must be paid to the potential ambiguous dynamics it may create, such as surfacing conflicts, or reproducing power imbalances (Froese et al., 2025). Thus, Froese et al. (2025) recommend that dissent, emotion, and context-specific dialogue be actively incorporated to help prevent the perpetuation of power imbalances.

Within co-creation processes, **co-design** plays a crucial role in the early stages of collaboration, where involved actors jointly frame problems, set priorities, and design interventions. **Co-development** follows by advancing strategies, policies, or technologies through iterative cycles of planning, testing, and refinement, ensuring that solutions remain sustainable and adaptable over time. Finally, **co-evaluation** complements these processes by engaging parties involved in the joint assessment of outcomes, impacts, and lessons learned, thereby strengthening accountability and facilitating continuous improvement (Franke et al., 2022; Vargas et al., 2022).

Another term that is often used in collaborative research projects is **co-production**, which refers to collaborative processes that bring together diverse expertise and experiences to create new knowledge, tools, products, activities, or outcomes. It is often described as an umbrella term for research engagement, which typically incorporates other co-processes, and often in a sequential manner (Fleming et al., 2023). A more specific form of co-production - **knowledge co-production** - emphasizes "iterative and collaborative processes involving diverse types of expertise, knowledge and actors to produce context-specific knowledge" (Norström et al., 2020, p. 183). This narrower definition highlights the integration of scientific, local, and practitioner knowledge to generate actionable insights tailored to particular contexts.

Although the terms **co-creation** and **co-production** are often used interchangeably in the literature (Voorberg et al., 2014), distinguishing between them clarifies their specific roles in participatory research. **Co-creation** can be understood as the overarching practice of collaborative value generation, while **co-production** and its variants highlight the processes of knowledge integration and application. Together with co-design, co-development, and co-evaluation, these approaches provide complementary pathways for structuring participation and fostering inclusive, practice-oriented innovation in the Living Lab context.

Box 1: Glossary

Social-ecological systems are complex, adaptive systems consisting of a bio-geophysical unit and its associated social actors and institutions. The spatial or functional boundaries of the system delimit a particular ecosystem and its problem context (Glaser et al., 2012). The intertwined social and ecological components and processes in social-ecological systems (SES) are often non-linear and interact across multiple levels and scales (Biggs et al., 2021, Cash et al., 2006, Folke et al., 2016). A social-ecological systems perspective highlights the need to understand both natural and social dynamics.

Actors (often referred to as stakeholders in earlier literature, see Reed et al., 2024) are individuals, groups, or organizations who affect, or are affected by decisions concerning a particular issue, such as marine extreme events. This term encompasses a wide range of parties of interest, including policymakers, practitioners, researchers, interest groups, end-users, citizens, communities, media and those directly impacted by environmental, social, or economic consequences. Actors may hold formal authority, provide expertise, represent collective interests, or embody lived experiences, and their involvement is essential for inclusive and effective governance (see Freeman, 1984; Reed, 2009, 2024).

Participation in research processes can be understood as the collaborative act that integrates diverse knowledge systems by involving different actors, e.g., communities, policymakers, lay-people and scientists in the research process (Reed et al., 2008) with the aim of encouraging involvement and engagement.

Living Labs are spatially defined spaces (e.g., a specific social-ecological setting) (Franke et al., 2022) or large-scale research infrastructures (Schneidewind et al., 2018), in which researchers and societal actors jointly experiment and co-design, co-develop/co-produce, and co-evaluate (Schäpke et al., 2018) scientifically and socially robust solutions to real-world sustainability problems (Schneidewind et al., 2018, Schäpke et al., 2018, WBGU, 2016). However, it needs to be acknowledged that there is a wide-spread understanding and no universally valid definition for Living Labs. The similar term “**Reallabor**” in Germany has two conceptual roots: the international Living Lab tradition from innovation studies, and the German Real-World Laboratory tradition from transformative sustainability research. While the terms are sometimes used interchangeably, they represent distinct schools of thought with different epistemologies, goals, and methodological lineages.

Co-creation is an overarching approach in which scientists, practitioners, organizations, and citizens work together to generate knowledge, develop solutions, and drive innovations. Often defined as the joint creation of value with active participation of end-users, essential to social innovation (Vargas et al., 2022; Voorberg et al., 2014).

Co-design is understood as a collaborative process in which diverse stakeholders jointly frame problems, set priorities, and design interventions to ensure relevance and legitimacy (Franke et al., 2022; Vargas et al., 2022).

Co-development is the collaborative advancement of strategies, policies, or technologies through iterative cycles of planning, testing, and refinement, ensuring long-term sustainability and adaptability (Franke et al., 2022).

Co-evaluation is a participatory process in which involved actors jointly assess outcomes, impacts, and lessons learned. It emphasizes accountability, reflexivity, and continuous improvement by integrating diverse perspectives into the evaluation of both methods and results (Franke et al., 2022).

Co-production is “an umbrella term for research engagement (which typically incorporates some or all of co-design, co-development, and co-delivery, often sequentially) that brings diverse knowledges together to create new knowledge, tools or products, activities, processes, and/or outcomes” (Fleming et al., 2023).

3 Implementation of participatory approaches and Living Labs in *mareXtreme*

In this section, we present an overview of the four collaborative projects within *mareXtreme*. Each project description highlights the relevant hazards, key actors, and anticipated outcomes of the participatory processes and Living Lab activities. Table 1 in Section 3.5 offers a synthesis of how the projects operate across different scales and levels, including their engagement with actors, institutional settings, and temporal dynamics. Together, these elements provide insights about the difference and similarities in the four *mareXtreme* projects, but as well help to identify potentials for synergies of participatory Living Labs approaches in the context of extreme events and coastal resilience.

3.1 METAScales - Multiscale modelling of marine extremes and their socio-economic impacts

METAScales looks into physical-oceanographic risks along the German North Sea coast. A particular focus is put on understanding future marine extremes, their impacts on society, technical systems, and nature, as well as the development of necessary reactive measures and preventive actions. To integrate these different scientific angles with each other and with practice and local communities on the ground, the transdisciplinary Living Lab approach is a core element for the collaborative development and facilitation of enhancing coastal resilience to marine hazards.

The Living Labs in METAScales are located in Wremen, Lower-Saxony, and on Nordstrand, Schleswig-Holstein. The identification of these locations is the result of a bottom-up decision-making process based on practical knowledge and experience from regional experts in the field of coastal protection, nature conservation, and disaster risk management, acquired through qualitative interviews and focus group discussions. The Living Labs bring together actors from science, civil society, local governments, and practice to collaboratively develop strategies for improved risk management, with a focus on integrating (community-based) disaster risk management and adaptation in coastal protection to deal with intensifying coastal risks. In both states, Lower-Saxony and Schleswig-Holstein, the Living Lab locations Wremen and Nordstrand are nestled in historically grown and institutionalised governance systems that shape dealing with marine hazards and other risks. These include on the one hand the preventive dike system, that protects the hinterland and prevents flooding, and on the other the reactive disaster management and emergency response institutions and respective procedures for disasters. What is currently missing, is a whole-of-society approach, that includes and empowers the civil society in dealing with natural hazards.

Addressing the challenge of bridging boundaries between established sectoral actors from practice, civil society and science, the METAScales team applies a specific Living Lab structure. The respective Living Lab Teams in both communities consist of individuals representing diverse parts of society covering businesses, associations, administration, education, and practice in DRM and coastal protection. These Teams focus on community-based disaster risk management through identifying local demands and challenges, developing possible solutions, and implementing these solutions in their communities. In addition to these Living Lab Teams, the Living Lab Advisory Boards consist of regional experts from coastal protection, DRM, and nature conservation, to support the co-production processes in the Living Lab Teams directly or indirectly with advice and overarching insights. Above all, these Advisory Boards act as a science-practice collaboration space with a focus on coastal protection, where the multi-disciplinary project scientists increasingly collaborate with practice through for example providing

scientific services, incorporating expressed needs into research, or comparing local experience with scientific results.

In order to achieve resilience, a whole-of-society approach within specific local contexts is essential, because we are facing challenges that impact the whole society with very different localised effects. Neither science, nor technological innovation alone can provide the one single solution to become resilient. It is an endeavour in which everyone has certain responsibilities and can make a contribution. A Living Lab can be an approach for transdisciplinary collaboration and bottom-up decision-making that facilitates local empowerment and ownership of coastal resilience strategies and measures.

Figure 4: Structure of the MetaScales Living Lab approach in Wremen and Nordstrand.
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3.2 PrimePrevention - Predicting marine biological hazards to prevent socio-economic impacts

PrimePrevention aims to improve the detection of marine biological hazards such as vibrio bacteria, cyanobacteria, and hypoxia in the Baltic Sea at an early stage and to mitigate their socio-economic impact. The goal is to accelerate the process from measurement to the targeted provision of information and knowledge to respective societal sectors, here specifically focussing on regional authorities. Relevant groups in connection with the three biological hazards include tourism, fisheries, the general public and the public authorities and agencies, particularly those responsible for the environment and health in the federal states of Schleswig-Holstein and Mecklenburg-Vorpommern. Under this regional umbrella, the PrimePrevention project focuses on three Baltic Sea coastal Living Labs: the Schlei (vibrio bacteria), Kiel Bight (hypoxia), and Greifswald Bodden (cyanobacteria). Additional analyses are being carried out at the Oderhaff (algal blooms, hypoxia). The focus is primarily on the cooperation with public authorities at the interface with science to further develop existing measurement methods and information systems. From a social science perspective, PrimePrevention aims to understand the functioning of current network structures that enable (or hinder) the flow of information necessary to respond adequately to marine biological hazards.

Furthermore, the project evaluates factors and processes of inter- and transdisciplinary knowledge co-production in the Living Lab context. To gain an understanding of the existing governance frame, various methodological approaches were combined to survey and analyse the networks in place:

- 1) Actor mapping (June–August 2024)
- 2) Interviews with key actors (since November 2024, ongoing)
- 3) Accompanying problem-focussed workshops (ongoing)

As part of the actor mapping process, relevant organisations and end-users were identified on the basis of their responsibilities, interests and regional connections and selected for in-depth interviews. The interviews were conducted via online meetings, recorded and then systematically evaluated. In addition, a succession of workshops is being held to identify the needs of various actor groups. For instance, in November 2024, an online workshop was held with representatives from public authorities to discuss the need for and improvement of measurement methods for cyanobacterial blooms. In addition, the HABBAL project (a collaborating project on algal blooms) organised a dialogue event in June 2025 with participants from research, administration and tourism organisations to exchange information on health risks posed by toxic algal blooms in the Baltic Sea. The aim of both workshops was to initiate an initial interdisciplinary dialogue, to provide information on known risks and existing knowledge gaps, and to jointly develop approaches for a sustainable information and early warning system.

First findings from the interviews suggest that information and reporting chains for the three biological hazards only exist to a limited extent and are not streamlined across the respective hazards and federal states. For example, while reporting chains about the occurrence of cyanobacteria blooms are already established in Schleswig-Holstein, in Mecklenburg-Vorpommern such processes are less established. Insights from the dialogue with participants from administration and tourism support this, as representatives of a tourism association criticise that they were not informed about the occurrence of a bloom, even though the health agency had determined its occurrence on a bathing beach. Additional to the barriers in communication of this hazard, interviewees point to institutional and practical barriers in the implementation of a reliable monitoring strategy: on the one hand shortcomings in personal and financial capacities hinder shorter monitoring intervals, on the other hand, the occurrence and disappearance of cyanobacteria blooms is highly dynamic, which complicates both monitoring and prediction. The authorities are therefore placing greater emphasis on comprehensive obligations to provide information (Informationspflicht) through information brochures or announcements, hoping that the transparent communication of marine hazard enables bathers to act responsibly. In the case of Vibrio bacteria, similar differences in monitoring strategies and reporting chains exist between federal states, which is largely due to the lack of regulatory frameworks. For hypoxia, currently there are no established reporting chains. One reason for this is that such events have not yet been systematically recorded or classified as reportable. There is also a lack of clear responsibilities and standardised procedures for assessing and communicating such occurrences.

Figure 5: Structure of the PrimePrevention Living Lab approach used for the Living Labs in the Baltic Sea. © C. Hoerterer

3.3 MULTI-MAREX - A Living Laboratory for improved forecasting and action options for multiple geomarine extreme events

MULTI-MAREX focuses on improving response and forecasting capacities for multiple geomarine extreme events — including earthquakes, volcanic eruptions, and tsunamis and their cascading events — in the Mediterranean Sea. Two Living Laboratories are established in the Aegean to study marine geological extreme events and their associated hazards, aiming to advance our understanding of their underlying drivers and consequences for disaster preparedness and risk management. These Living Labs co-develop application-oriented knowledge for managing marine geohazards at the so-called last mile. MULTI-MAREX unites scientists, authorities, coastal communities, and other actors to jointly co-design and co-develop strategies and measures that enhance adaptive capacity and protection in coastal communities. Extreme geomarine events have serious short- and long-term consequences for coastal communities. Early warning and disaster prevention pose both societal and political challenges for which the consortium provides the necessary expertise to deal with these hazards at various levels. Strengthening community disaster preparedness will be achieved by establishing seamless land-to-sea monitoring, enhancing rapid-response capabilities and co-developing community-owned preparedness strategies and institutionalized communication channels.

In 2025, the Santorini seismic sequence exemplified a new category of marine geohazard. Although no major earthquake, tsunami, or volcanic eruption occurred, the persistent seismic tremors, linked to magma migration beneath the islands of Santorini and Amorgos (Isken et al., 2025), had substantial socio-economic impacts on the tourism sector. More than 30,000 low-magnitude earthquakes prompted a government-declared state of emergency, the evacuation of residents, and widespread uncertainty among visitors. Tour operators and cruise lines altered itineraries, leading to a marked decline in

tourist arrivals despite the absence of structural damage. This ripple effect illustrates the political as well as societal embeddedness of extremes and demonstrates how marine geological events causing no physical destruction may nonetheless generate significant economic disruption. Physical devastation or loss of life would have resulted in even more severe damage and in even higher economic losses.

Even before the crisis reached its peak, our Greek MULTI-MAREX affiliates contacted us to request technical and scientific support. Within days, MULTI-MAREX launched a rapid-response mission and seafloor and onshore instruments were deployed to obtain precise seismic and geodetic data and to assess whether the ongoing activity would escalate or diminish. Moreover, the mission aimed to evaluate secondary hazards, including landslide risks along steep coastal sectors and the potential for tsunami generation should larger earthquakes occur. The MULTI-MAREX engagement in the crisis was multifaceted: we shared data and analysis results with the Greek institutes involved in the response, coordinated international scientific analyses of the ongoing events, and led the marine geophysical efforts in the region. Critically, we provided input to the national Crisis Response Committee, thereby directly informing the Greek government and Prime Minister Mitsotakis throughout the crisis. The results were communicated not only to Greek authorities and the scientific community but also to the broader public. A summary and FAQ were published on the MULTI-MAREX website, and the project contributed to extensive media outreach. MULTI-MAREX members gave dozens of radio and TV interviews in Germany, Greece, and across Europe, with media coverage featuring MULTI-MAREX contributions in more than 3,000 media outputs.

This crisis, and our support of the Greek authorities, demonstrates the effectiveness of the MULTI-MAREX approach to improving hazard management in the Aegean and highlights its potential transferability to other regions. Central to this approach was the co-creation of mitigation measures and application-oriented knowledge through the joint efforts of scientists from Germany and Greece, local authorities and government entities, media and science communication experts, and local communities. This collaboration proved not only effective and timely, but also illustrated how coastal regions can be supported in strengthening their resilience to geomarine hazards. A key pillar to improving hazard prevention and management are thus the Living Laboratories that we establish in Kalamata and Santorini because they are the nucleus of launching joint efforts and collaboration with stakeholders/authorities. For the establishment of the Living Labs, MULTI-MAREX carried out two Fact Finding Missions (FFM) in 2025. The team conducted the first FFM in Kalamata, Greece, to initiate a collaborative disaster-risk reduction strategy for marine-related hazards. Local authorities and sectoral actors contributed to joint assessments of vulnerabilities such as earthquakes, tsunamis, floods, storm surges, and coastal erosion. Field surveys and geodata collection will support future modelling and hazard analyses. The partners agreed to develop a Living Lab aligned with the UNESCO-IOC “Tsunami Ready” framework, formalizing cooperation through Letters of Intent. An evacuation exercise and review of existing protection measures marked the beginning of a long-term, science-informed effort to strengthen preparedness at the community level.

Likewise, the second MULTI-MAREX FFM in Santorini comprised coordinated engagements with regional authorities, municipal leaders, the scientific community, schools, and field-measurement teams to advance a shared, science-based approach to volcanic- and earthquake-related risk on Santorini. Meetings with the Vice-Governor and key economic associations highlighted the need for reliable risk communication,

centralised official messaging, and strengthened volcanic monitoring structures. Discussions with the Mayor and civil-protection representatives focused on refining evacuation planning, verifying designated assembly points through scientific modelling, and enhancing risk awareness through the education sector. Joint participation in the national “YFHAISTIS 2025” campaign enabled extensive exchange with Greek universities and agencies on monitoring strategies and data integration, while promising access to high-value geodetic and topographic datasets. Educational workshops with approximately 500 scholars supported local capacity building and public understanding of georisks. Parallel RTK-GNSS, photogrammetric and drone surveys provided essential baseline data on ground deformation and coastal morphology. Collectively, these activities reinforced strong local demand for evidence-based preparedness and consolidated a long-term collaborative framework for risk mitigation. Both FFM delivered Memorandum of Understanding and Collaboration agreements which opened the door for the MULTI-MAREX team to officially establish the Living Labs.

The Living Lab activities in Santorini and Kalamata are fully grounded in co-design methodology. Experiences and expertise on extreme events, disaster risk reduction, and geodata were mutually exchanged with municipal and regional authorities, civil society partners and Greek research institutions and academic partners, and cooperation agreements were signed. Fact-finding missions and in-person consultations in Greece and Germany, combined with rapid-response actions during the Santorini 2025 seismic crisis, were used to identify gaps in hazard perception and local preparedness. This framework enables genuine co-design and the activities demonstrate how integrated offshore–onshore data acquisition, advanced analytical methods (including machine learning), and close collaboration with authorities, responsible actors and civil society representatives can produce decision-ready, application-oriented knowledge. By linking scientific observations, long-term archives, numerical modelling and Living Lab formats, MULTI-MAREX is building a generic and transferable methodological approach to strengthen coastal resilience to geomarine hazards in the Aegean and beyond, and will thus support communities not only to understand extreme geo-marine events, but to actively shape preparedness and response strategies. In this way, the Living Labs build resilience as a shared, participatory practice at the science–policy–society interface.

Figure 6: Structure of the MULTI-MAREX Living Lab approach used for the LLs in Santorini and Kalamata. © R. Benavides & J. Karstens

3.4 ElbeXtreme - Monitoring and modelling of extreme events in the Elbe estuary and the German Bight

The main goal of ElbeXtreme is to assess the impacts of extreme events, particularly fluvial floods, droughts, heatwaves, and storm surges, on estuarine and coastal ecosystems and their associated services. Building on this foundation, the project team analyses the related and cascading risks to society and the economy. The team works with existing datasets, develops innovative observational approaches, and generates new data products, partially in co-creation approaches with relevant actors, that describe the physical, chemical, and biological states of the Elbe River, its estuary, and its outflow into the North Sea. Integrating existing and newly acquired data through quantitative as well as conceptual modelling enables the development of an Elbe Digital Twin, which enhances our understanding of how extreme events alter ecosystem services and related risks.

Currently, the project uses the entire Elbe estuary–coastal system as a case study. This perspective allows ElbeXtreme to assess large-scale ecosystems and their interactions with extremes in a less place-based manner, focussing on their functions across time and space. In these offshore and marine contexts, visible, place-based communities and therefore the number of directly engaged actors is limited. Certain ecosystem functions in focus are not characterized by a clear experiential visibility and tangibility for involved actors. The governance of these systems and their interaction with extremes is tied to institutional actors with legal mandates, at the interface of extreme events, ecosystems, and the economy. ElbeXtreme addresses these actors specifically in parallel to the assessments on the systems that they govern and contributes thereby to the establishment of a co-creation network that can support potential future Living Lab focussed localization of adaptation pathways in forthcoming project phases.

The Elbe Estuary and the German Bight host diverse ecosystems that are strongly influenced by economic activities, including intensive agriculture on fertile estuarine soils and the operations of the Port of Hamburg with its extensive logistics network. The project team engages with key economic sectors in the region, such as shipping and logistics, agriculture, tourism, nature conservation, fishing, and energy. The ecosystems under investigation include alluvial forests, salt marshes, reed beds, and seagrass meadows, as well as aquatic systems such as tidal flats, mussel beds, kelp forests, and pelagic habitats. To assess the impact of extreme events on these ecosystems and the services they provide to regional actors, the project mainly collaborates with organisational actors. These actors include representatives from the aforementioned sector chambers, water authorities, elected city and regional officials, and nature conservation organisations.

The concept of 'Nature's Contributions to People' visualises the integrated nature of natural and social systems. Here, it is used to evaluate how extreme events affect the contributions that ecosystems provide to the socio-economic system. From a social science research perspective, the project team aims to understand which risks are perceived as most significant by different actor groups (e.g., economic sectors and decision-making authorities), how these risks relate to the contributions provided by the focal ecosystems, and where potential opportunities for change lie within these interactions. In a later phase of the project, the ElbeXtreme team plans to co-design and co-create early warning and adaptation pathways with place-specific actor groups in designated Living Labs.

To gain an understanding of the perceived risks of extremes and their relation to nature's contributions to people, various methodological approaches are employed:

- 1) Actor mapping and interviews with key actors
- 2) Visioning and conceptual modelling workshop
- 3) Ecosystem-focused risk prioritisation workshops
- 4) Scenario development and future risk workshop

The actor mapping process identified and confirmed relevant high- and mid-level decision-making organisations through selected interviews with priority actors. This core group of actors was subsequently invited to a visioning and conceptual modelling workshop in February 2025. On the workshop day itself, the group worked in mixed teams to develop a positive future vision for the Elbe estuary and German Bight, subsequently co-creating conceptual risk models using the Impact Web methodology. These models were integrated into one system using KUMU, validated against literature, and will be used as a basis to link co-created work related to nature's contributions to people, as well as research results from ecosystem-specific working groups within the project team.

The results of the visioning and conceptual risk modelling workshop show that stronger coordination and integrated, cross-sectoral governance can significantly reduce the risks posed by extreme events by aligning coastal and inland flood management and balancing ecological and economic goals. Actors agree that a systemic perspective is essential, as aquatic heatwaves, low flows, storm surges, and floods are interconnected and affect multiple sectors, requiring holistic and cross-sectoral strategies. Healthy ecosystems are central to resilience, since their protection and restoration strengthen ecological integrity, support human well-being, and enhance adaptive capacity. Sediment management appears as a key aspect involving the mandate and interest of key actors, such as the Hamburg Port Authority, the Federal Waterways Engineering and Research Institute as well as the Federal Maritime and Hydrographic Agency. In that sense sediment management could serve as a strategic lever, linking ecological and economic challenges while offering opportunities to reduce environmental stress and improve navigation safety. Focusing on key leverage points—such as ecosystem resilience, sediment management, and critical infrastructure—enables targeted and effective adaptation and risk reduction. These results and the conceptual model will be linked with ecosystem-focused knowledge and future risks work linked to co-created scenarios that we hope to co-develop in a series of regional mini-workshops and in two further core-actor workshops planned for December 2025 and mid-2026.

Figure 7: Structure of the ElbeXtreme Living Lab approach used for the LLs in the Elbe Estuary Region Geesthacht-German Bight. © L.-M. Schmidbauer & J. O'Connor

3.5. Mini-Synthesis of *mareXtreme* projects: Working across scales and levels of engagement when addressing extreme events at the coast

Table 1 below synthesises how the projects operate across different scales and levels, including their engagement with actors, institutional settings, and temporal dynamics. When Living Labs are applied to the study of extreme events at the coast, the question of scale and level becomes particularly important. Extreme events unfold across multiple dimensions, and Living Labs must be able to capture these dynamics to coordinate societal responses. Following Gibson et al. (2000) and Cash et al. (2006), we understand scale as an underlying dimension (e.g., spatial, temporal, quantitative, or analytical), and level as the unit of analysis situated along a given scale.

The table maps how the four *mareXtreme* projects position themselves within these scales and levels, and identifies what needs to be taken into account when operating and researching within them. This comparative perspective helps clarify how research can more effectively address marine extreme events and contributes to improved risk management by highlighting which scales and levels are most critical for engagement and what we can learn in relation to participation. It also illustrates how Living Labs can function as research infrastructures that connect diverse actors across governance levels, knowledge domains, and practices and therefore lays the foundation for a blueprint of Living Labs in the context of extreme events and coastal resilience.

Table 1: Synthesis of the Living Lab cases in *mareXtreme*.

Scale	Location of <i>mareXtreme</i> Projects on the presented scales			
	ElbeXtreme	METAscales	Multi-Marex	PrimePrevention
Spatial (e.g., patches, landscapes, regions, globe)	Sector- and Ecosystem related decision-makers from federal state level, city level and municipality level.	Focus on local communities for co-development and testing of solutions in the Living Lab Teams. In addition, focus on regional, and federal state administration for political and governance contexts of coastal protection, drainage, and disaster management. And focus on supra-regional context for the drivers of marine hazards threatening the German coastline. The following content for METAscales in this table refers to the Living Lab locations on community level.	At the local scale, specific coastal municipalities such as Kalamata and Santorini serve as the core of the Living Lab approach, where authorities, citizens, and scientists collaboratively co-design and test risk-response measures. At the regional scale, the focus shifts to connecting multiple coastal areas across the Eastern Mediterranean, including zones influenced by the Hellenic Arc, addressing the political and governance contexts of coastal protection and disaster management. At the transnational scale, these Living Labs form a Mediterranean-wide network linking institutions and stakeholders, capturing the supra-regional drivers of marine hazards threatening Eastern Mediterranean coastlines.	While the natural science research mainly takes place at the ecosystem/landscape level (our Living Labs), the governance analysis is performed at the level of the federal states.
Temporal (e.g., daily, weekly, yearly OR long/short duration)	Fluvial floods, droughts, heatwaves, and storm surges and their effects on ecosystem as well as ecosystem services have different temporality reaching from hours to years.	Focus on both: reaction to rapid onset and sudden disaster scenarios, as well as long-term establishment of risk awareness, self-efficacy and coping capacities.	Dual focus: rapid-response to sudden geological events as well as fast-response to quick onsets. Support establishment of long-term risk awareness in the population. Support guidelines design.	Duration of the occurrence of biological hazards last from hours (cyanobacteria occurrence at the beach) to several weeks (e.g., hypoxia events in seawater near the seabed). Additionally, the frequency of the occurrence is seasonal (summer month), but may also happen multiple times per season.
Jurisdictional (e.g., local, provincial, national, international)	Depending on the risk from national (e.g., dyke regulations) to federal (e.g. sediment management) or	Focus on local informal structures. Within the frame of municipality (Gemeinde) and county (Landkreis); and state-	Regional at community level (Kalamata and Santorini). Later National at Greek level.	Administration of issues is mainly on state-level ("Ländersache"), The corresponding level would be provincial.

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	local (e.g. port management)	level (Bundesland) (Generalplan Küstenschutz)		
Institutional (e.g., operating rules, laws and regulations, constitutions)	Certain aspects are within the legal obligations of state- or municipal organizations (e.g., flood protection and management). Other aspects however, such as the understudied effects of extremes on ecosystems, are not yet sufficiently institutionalized.	Mainly informal capacities and community networks to deal with risks and disasters	Function within a multi-level institutional framework connecting local municipalities, regional authorities, and national civil protection structures following national regulations on hazard management. Co-design protocols and participatory rules ensure transparent and inclusive collaboration among all stakeholders.	Monitoring of cyanobacteria is mandatory due to the bad <i>environmental status</i> of the Baltic sea, which is regulated at EU level in the Marine Strategy Framework Directive and Water Framework Directive.
Management (e.g., tasks, projects, strategies)	Management of risks from extremes is mainly at strategy level as it often refers to larger infrastructure projects. Ecosystem-based work however, often operates on project level.	Management consists of a local and area-based strategy with multiple tasks and roles throughout the communities.	Management of extreme geo-marine events is mainly at strategy level under the umbrella of larger joint projects.	Management of marine biological hazards is mainly at task level, as responses to the occurrence of hazards is mainly dealt with as specific interventions, e.g., issuing of warnings at the beach.
Networks Levels to be decided	Different networks exist in the context of hazard early warning and response. In the context of ecosystems however more specific networks are needed.	Networks within the Living Lab communities with a focus on bringing warnings across to all members of the community, to understand them, and to act accordingly (e.g. last mile networks)	Information produced could be immediately delivered to Greek authorities. Decisions lie and fall under Greek National Risk Response Guidelines at National Gov level. Co-design within Living Labs can be transferred to local and regional communities.	The most important networks are the reporting and information/communication chains (Meldekettten) in relation to the occurrence of biological hazards. Further analyses include the investigation of other resource flows, such as financial, human, and other forms of capitals within networks.
Intensity of involvement (e.g., information, consultation, collaboration, empowerment, see comment) (Kruetly et al., 2010)	Consultation and collaboration with selected decision-makers. Information to a wider range of actors and in the future empowerment through more place-specific work.	Empowerment of communities to build capacities for better dealing with extremes and disasters; and collaboration with regional actors to adapt coastal protection to increasing marine extremes	High-precision, latest and state of the art data, information and consultation to highest Greek authorities as well as collaboration with Greek and international partners in science, academia and stakeholders. Future Living Lab tasks will develop into empowerment of communities.	Depending on the WP, the interactions with relevant decision-makers and end users range from the provision of information (e.g., analysis of socio-economic consequences regarding shifts in ecosystem service provision, or models for the prediction of oxygen deficiency areas), to consultation (e.g., reporting on expected ecosystem service changes from society to science in form of a questionnaire) to collaboration (joint collaboration for the development of a sensor with fishers). The endproducts of PP are intended to contribute to

				“empowerment” in the form of technological transfer of project results.
Land-Sea Interface (on land, at the coast, in the sea)	Our project covers land and river areas as well as coastal and marine systems.	On land and at the coast	On land and at the coast as well as the last mile efforts focusing on phase I in Greece (Kalamata and Santorini)	On the coast, which includes the occurrence of biological hazards in coastal waters (up to 10 nautical miles) and on land (the beach).
Extend of Impact (e.g., patches, landscapes, regions, globe)	Landscape and region	Local in the community with transferability opportunities in the whole municipality and beyond	Community and transferable to many other coastal communities and cities along the Mediterranean.	Vibrio and cyanobacteria mainly occur at patch-level, while hypoxia may extend to the landscape level.
Predictability	Hazards are fairly predictable (with different degrees of certainty). Impacts on ecosystems, ecosystem services and social-economic systems are not predictable.	Generally, well established predictability of storm surges and weather forecast. Nevertheless, sudden-onset disasters due to e.g. failing infrastructure or overwhelming compound events remain (almost) unpredictable.	Not predictable but current and future sensor networks could assist in immediate information (=interpreted data) transfer to decision makers. Impacts predictability low: Depending on Geological impact.	Vibrio outbreaks are currently not predictable. Cyanobacteria blooms can be predicted to some extent; however, they remain highly dynamic and are subject to rapid changes due to varying biophysical conditions. Hypoxia extent and predictability is uncertain, and further information or methods for forecasting are currently unclear.
Others?			Geological sub-surface/submarine events are highly unpredictable. Impact unpredictable. Socio-economic impact is unpredictable.	

4 Discussion

Drawing on the experiences of the four *mareXtreme* projects with applying a Living Lab approach, we here outline the opportunities & challenges of Living Lab approaches for dealing with extreme events at the coast, as well as its added value beyond 'traditional' transdisciplinary research.

4.1 Opportunities of using a Living Lab approach

The possibilities vary depending on the specific needs, ranging from technical and technological testing sites to places where social transformation in enhancing disaster risk management is initiated and accompanied.

From a **technological perspective**, Living Labs can support technical system performance, operational readiness, and innovation in hazard management. For example, Living Labs can strengthen early warning by providing a space to train, test, and refine measures for reducing the socio-economic effects after an extreme event, which is commonly referred to as the "last mile" of End-to-End Early Warning Systems (see UNISDR, 2006; Waidyanatha, 2010). In the chain of measures after an extreme event a seamless, routine approach with an engaged public is crucial to lower vulnerability and guarantee that the steps taken are effective. This is particularly true because an initial extreme event may trigger other events, and the cascading effects of such compound events may amplify the negative impact along a given coastal stretch by a certain factor, or even order of magnitude. Examples of such compound events affect the geohazards (e.g., an earthquake or submarine volcanic eruption may cause a slope or flank to collapse, and the resulting landslide may even cause a tsunami), biohazards (a marine heatwave may cause toxic algal blooms and decreased oxygen solubility, both of which promote anoxia) and also meteorological and oceanographic hazards (storms may cause surges, dyke breaks, flooding but also be followed by turbidity currents or meteo-tsunamis). A Living Lab approach thus allows actors to explore and understand complex hazard chains and the technological interdependencies of multi-hazard dynamics.

From a **sustainability governance and community-driven development perspective**, Living Labs offer a powerful means to strengthen social resilience, participatory governance, and community ownership of risk strategies in coastal regions. Much like they provide a space for developing, training, and testing early-warning technologies, Living Labs create an environment for co-creative knowledge exchange in which diverse actors jointly identify crucial steps for adaptation and preparedness. By fostering self-efficacy and community empowerment, they support the development of locally owned preparedness strategies that embed resilience within existing knowledge systems, everyday practices, and governance structures. At the same time, Living Labs enable reflection and dialogue on priorities, uncover underlying assumptions, and open up discussions that might otherwise remain implicit. Through active engagement in co-creation processes, they also contribute to education and awareness-building around natural phenomena, helping communities better understand the dynamics of marine extreme events and the options available for responding to them.

4.2 Challenges of using a Living Lab approach

While a Living Lab approach offers substantial opportunities to align research objectives more closely with societal needs and objectives, its participatory nature often makes it also significantly more challenging. Such challenges arise for example in relation to actor responsibilities, risk communication, ethical and power-related pitfalls throughout the Living Lab process, and the evaluation and long-term sustainability of project outputs.

Actor responsibilities

From an actor-oriented perspective, Living Labs face particular challenges due to the heterogeneity of actor constellations involved. In many cases, actor landscapes are characterized by fragmented responsibilities and overlapping mandates, which can complicate coordination and blur accountability across the process. Responsibility for mitigating and managing impacts of environmental hazards often lies with public authorities, while the consequences are primarily experienced by local communities and lay-people. This creates structural asymmetries in agency, power, and access to resources, which may hinder equitable participation and limit the influence of less empowered actors within co-creative processes.

These challenges are further amplified in offshore and marine contexts, where the number of directly engaged actors is often limited. In areas such as the German Bight, the relative absence of visible, place-based communities and the dominance of institutional or sectoral actors can reduce the diversity of perspectives and constrain participatory dynamics. Moreover, the willingness of actors to engage is strongly shaped by the experiential visibility and tangibility of environmental changes and risks. Hazards or ecosystem changes that are less directly perceptible tend to generate lower levels of public engagement, which can further exacerbate existing participation gaps and challenge the inclusiveness and effectiveness of Living Lab approaches.

Risk communication

From a risk communication perspective, Living Labs face substantial challenges due to the inherent uncertainty, and temporal dynamics of environmental hazards. Many of the risks addressed in Living Lab contexts are characterized by cascading and compound events, which are difficult and partially impossible to anticipate, model, and communicate in an accessible way that addresses uncertainty. The interdependencies between different hazard types, as well as their potential to amplify one another, require the integration of diverse forms of scientific knowledge, including probabilistic assessments and scenario-based projections. Translating this into formats that are meaningful and actionable for a broad range of actors can be particularly challenging within co-creative processes, where differing levels of expertise and risk literacy and uncertainty tolerance must be reconciled.

In addition, participation dynamics in Living Labs are often closely linked to the temporal occurrence of extreme events. Engagement levels tend to be highest in the immediate aftermath of a disaster, when risks are tangible and salient, but typically decline over time as the immediacy of the threat fades. Sustaining long-term engagement beyond these peak moments remains a key challenge, particularly in the absence of continuous or visible risk signals. This dynamic is further complicated by the phenomenon of “disaster-oblivion“, where past events lose their perceived relevance, reducing motivation for ongoing preparedness and adaptation efforts.

Moreover, there is frequently a misalignment between scientifically defined risk priorities and the perceived relevance of these risks among local actors. Hazards that are considered critical from a scientific or technological perspective may not resonate with the lived experiences or immediate concerns of actors, which can limit their willingness to engage in co-creation processes. Living Labs must therefore navigate not only the communication of uncertain and difficult risk information, but also the challenge of bridging these perception gaps in order to foster shared understanding and sustained participation.

Ethical and power-related pitfalls

From an ethical and power-related perspective, Living Labs are confronted with a range of challenges that stem from structural inequalities and the risk of reproducing existing imbalances within participatory processes. In particular, Living Labs must avoid forms of “parachute science”, where research is conducted in a top-down manner without meaningful local involvement, leading to extractive knowledge practices and limited long-term benefits for participating communities. This challenge is especially highlighted in high-risk settings that involve clear legal mandates of certain actor groups. Closely related to this are asymmetries in information, power, and decision-making authority, which can influence whose knowledge is recognized, whose voices are prioritized, and ultimately whose interests are reflected in the outcomes of the process.

These imbalances are often reinforced through unequal participation patterns. Due to differences in available time, financial resources, and institutional support, certain groups tend to be overrepresented in Living Lab settings, including government employees, representatives of organized interest groups, and retirees. At the same time, other perspectives remain systematically underrepresented, particularly those of private sector actors, women*, especially those with caregiving responsibilities, and younger people. Such disparities can limit the diversity of knowledge and experiences incorporated into co-creation processes and risk biasing outcomes toward the interests of more readily available or institutionally embedded actors. A key underlying factor in these participation gaps lies in resource constraints and the design of engagement formats. Time-intensive or inflexible co-creation formats, such as full-day workshops or narrowly scheduled meetings, may unintentionally exclude participants who cannot easily accommodate such commitments. As a result, Living Labs must carefully consider how participation opportunities are structured and communicated, ensuring that they are accessible and inclusive across different social groups and professional contexts. Without such reflexivity, there is a risk that Living Labs, despite their participatory ambition, reproduce rather than mitigate existing inequalities in power and representation.

Added value beyond transdisciplinary research

Beyond advancing transdisciplinary research, the Living Lab approach creates an animated, practice-oriented environment in which scientific insights can be co-created and tested for their real-world applicability in forecasting, measuring, and handling extreme events and their cascading impacts. This setting enables concepts to be adapted and better understood in real time as new hazards emerge or existing hazards intensify, ensuring that scientific knowledge remains operationally relevant. At the same time, Living Labs strengthen community disaster preparedness by highlighting and supporting self-efficacy in establishing seamless land-to-sea monitoring, enhancing rapid-response capabilities, and supporting the co-development of community-owned preparedness strategies and institutionalized communication channels.

5 Conclusion

Bringing together the conceptual foundations of the Living Lab approach, as technological test sites and places of societal processes, with theories of participation and co-creation, and situating these within the context of marine extreme events and coastal risks, we suggest that an integration of the different approaches - sustainability-oriented community development with technologically driven innovation initiatives - is needed to respond to the needs of coastal communities affected by coastal marine extreme events and authorities responsible for effective risk management. Participation in this context is meant as incorporating all actors involved and concerned on different levels and across scales depending on the goals and objectives addressed, ranging from political decision makers, federal and regional administration agencies, community responsibilities to lay-people affected by increasing marine hazards and their cumulative effects. Living Labs are research infrastructures in which co-creation and co-production are enabled, steered and supported, and considered as tools for inclusive, context-sensitive and empowering practices to achieve the mission's goal of promoting coastal resilience.

The four different project approaches demonstrate a broad range of understandings each of which contribute to a different angle of addressing the required management and adaptation strategies to increasing hazards in coastal systems. As discussed here, there are opportunities and challenges that arise by undertaking transdisciplinary research, realizing participatory engagement, and applying the Living Lab approach. The four different project angles elucidated the case-specific, place-specific and context-specific needs to integrate the scale of institutional actors with legal mandates and local communities that "feel" the impacts of these extremes but often have limited options to facilitate change. A common ground, based on the origins of living lab work, bringing together predominantly sustainability-oriented community development with technologically oriented innovation initiatives help to identify the distinctiveness and singularity of coastal living labs and supports an integrated coastal living lab approach for dealing with extreme events.

The collaboration in *mareXtreme* opens up the floor for a blueprint of marine and coastal Living Labs and their use not only as research infrastructure but as well as the basis for institutionalised collaboration in the adaptation to and management of land-sea extremes and building a sustainable legacy for after the mission's end. We will continue working towards this common goal in *mareXtreme*.

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